

PECULIARITIES OF PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF SECONDARY IMMUNODEFICIENCY IN ANIMAL HELMINTHIASES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of literature data on immunodeficiency in animal helminthiases. Parasites, through their immunosuppressive impact on the immunological status, can significantly aggravate processes within the immune system, promoting the development of immunodeficient states. Parasitic diseases suppress immune responses, leading to the development of secondary persistent immunodeficiency due to the inadequacy of the body's natural defense mechanisms. When infected with helminths, the human body mobilizes all its defense mechanisms; however, in some cases, when the fight against parasites is prolonged, immune reactions become inadequate, which may result in immunopathological manifestations and dysfunctions of various organs.*

Keywords: *helminthiases, immunity, secondary immunodeficiency.*

Relevance

Parasites, through their immunosuppressive impact on the immunological status, can significantly aggravate processes within the immune system, promoting the development of immunodeficient states and, as a result, increasing susceptibility to various diseases [4, 23]. All available scientific data indicate that immunity in helminthiases represents a unique example of evolutionary mutual adaptation between parasite and host. Immunity in helminthiases is characterized by low intensity, short duration, polymorphism, and low specificity due to the inadequacy of the body's natural defense mechanisms [8, 16].

Currently, immunocorrection methods are being increasingly applied in veterinary medicine. This is due to the fact that in the pathogenesis of many infectious, invasive, and other diseases in animals, the inadequacy of the body's natural defenses plays a significant role, leading to severe illness. In recent years, immunodeficient states in animals are being diagnosed more frequently, necessitating appropriate corrective measures [1, 12].

In recent times, veterinary science has extensively conducted research on determining immune status and methods for its correction in parasitic diseases. In helminthiases, deeper studies on the immunobiological status, the impact of anthelmintics, and immunoregulatory agents on the immune system of animals have been carried out by researchers. It has been established that helminths directly affect the functional activity of the immune system, leading to a state of secondary immunodeficiency. The use of anthelmintics often reduces immune status and does not yield the desired effect. Alongside anthelmintics, authors recommend the use of immunocorrective agents [9, 26].

In this context, a fundamentally new treatment method based on bioregulation of the body using immunostimulatory drugs of various origins is being developed [14, 19]. According to literature data, the mechanism of action of immunostimulants is based on the effect of nonspecific

protection, primarily phagocytosis. The defense system also includes spontaneous cellular cytotoxicity, with macrophages, polymorphonuclear leukocytes, T-cell precursors, T- and B-lymphocytes acting as effectors. Spontaneous cellular cytotoxicity depends on the mediators produced by these cells. In veterinary practice, for correcting primary and secondary immunodeficient states in animals, vitamins, microelements, adaptogens, imidazole derivatives (levamisole, tetramisole), bacterial preparations (pyrogenal, prodigiosan), nucleic acids, immune response mediators – cytomedines, and biologically active preparations are used [3, 19].

There is comparatively little information in the literature about the use of immunoregulatory agents in protozoal diseases of animals. Currently, scientific literature has a significant amount of theoretical and experimental material characterizing various aspects of the host immune response to helminth antigens [11]. However, the features of immunopathological reactions in helminthiases and their dependence on the specificity of the "parasite-host" system remain insufficiently studied. Clarifying these issues will enable targeted searches for ways to enhance the immunoreactivity of animals and create effective immunoprophylactic and immunodiagnostic drugs.

The aim of the study is to analyze literature data on the pathogenetic mechanisms of secondary immunodeficiency caused by animal parasites. The issue of secondary immunodeficiencies is one of the most relevant in veterinary helminthology. Immunodeficient states develop as a result of disruptions in immunogenesis processes, the mechanisms of which are not well understood in parasitic diseases in general and helminthiases in particular [3, 17].

The term "immunodeficiencies" refers to disturbances in the normal immune status caused by a defect in one or more mechanisms of the immune response [10]. Congenital (primary) and acquired (secondary) immunodeficiencies are usually distinguished. Primary immunodeficiencies refer to the innate inability of the body to perform a particular protective function within the overall immune process. It is noteworthy that there are numerous studies in the scientific literature on the morphofunctional features of various parts of the immune system, as well as the etiology and pathogenesis of congenital immunodeficiencies [16].

Unlike primary immunodeficiencies, secondary immune insufficiency is not associated with a genetic block of any component of the immune system but develops under the influence of various damaging factors. Among the factors leading to the development of secondary immunodeficiency, chemical factors, such as the use of medicinal products and plant protection agents (pesticides), cause justified concern [1, 24].

Disruptions in the normal immune response in helminthiases imply a negative influence of these parasites on the course of the disease, which has been confirmed in several studies [5, 21]. Research on the impact of parasitoses on changes in the cytokine profile is limited, and the results obtained are somewhat contradictory. Reliable information on the influence of concomitant helminthiases can lead to a reduction in the duration of the disease, a decrease in the intensity of its manifestations, and a reduction in cases of bacterial complications due to timely diagnosis and adequate therapy of concomitant parasitoses [7, 18].

Adhering to general physiological principles, immunity in helminthiases has its peculiarities, which depend on the parasite-host relationships, and the physiological and ecological characteristics of the helminths [13]. There are no helminths that cause only local changes in the host organism. The changes occurring in organs and tissues during helminthiases indicate metabolic disorders, the presence of dystrophic processes, allergic, and immunomorphological

reactions, i.e., they are the organism's response to the pathogenic action of the helminth. The degree of pathological changes depends on the type of pathogen, the intensity of the invasion, and the immunological status of the animals [21].

The nature of pathological and immunological processes in helminthiases, unlike infectious diseases, is largely determined by the morphological and biological characteristics of helminths. Despite significant common pathogenic factors caused by the agents of helminthiases and infectious diseases (toxigenic, antigenic, enzymatic, etc.), helminths exhibit several substantial biological and physiological peculiarities. The primary distinction is the larger size of helminths [17, 22]. Some small helminths measure in millimeters, with larvae up to 0.5 mm. The sizes of other even small helminths exceed the cellular elements of various tissues and blood elements of the host by more than ten times. Thus, the protective function of cellular elements is carried out differently than in infectious diseases. Fundamental differences between helminth agents and infectious agents also exist in their type of reproduction: microbes and viruses primarily reproduce quickly by simple division, while helminths reproduce slowly through sexual means [1, 18].

Helminths develop in stages, transitioning from a free-living parasitic stage, moving from one host to another, and from one organ to another through hematogenous, lymphogenous migration, passing through the liver, lungs, lymph nodes, etc. [12, 27]. In geohelminthiases, the pathogens develop to the invasive stage without an intermediate host in an "abiotic" environment. In contrast, the invasive stages of biohelminths develop in a "biotic" environment (e.g., mollusks, earthworms, various insects, mites, crustaceans, vertebrates). The impact of climatic and anthropogenic factors on them is more diverse. It is assumed that each stage of the helminth has its specific antigen [10].

Although it has been shown that various protozoan and helminth parasites activate different mechanisms of innate immunity, these organisms often survive and reproduce in their hosts because they are well-adapted to withstand host defenses. The primary innate immune response to protozoans is phagocytosis, but many of these parasites are resistant to phagocytic destruction and can even replicate within macrophages. Phagocytes can also attack helminth parasites and release bactericidal substances to destroy organisms too large for phagocytosis. However, many helminths have thick coverings that make them resistant to the cytotoxic (lytic) mechanisms of neutrophils and macrophages, and they are too large to be engulfed by phagocytes [15, 20].

Thus, helminths, localizing in various organs and tissues of the host, not only feed on its juices, blood, and food (in the intestines) but also cause dystrophic, atrophic, immunological changes, as well as dysbacteriosis. Therefore, deworming of animals should be supported by additional symptomatic and pathogenetic therapy.

Addressing the challenges associated with the growth and widespread prevalence of secondary immunodeficiencies of various etiologies, which are accompanied by numerous pathological processes, primarily necessitates morphofunctional studies of the immune system's state. Immune deficiency leads to decreased effectiveness of traditional therapy, promotes the activation of conditionally pathogenic microflora, changes in the pathogen, and superinfection, resulting in prolonged disease, complications, and in some cases, death. Numerous scientific studies conducted domestically and internationally have shown that restoring the functional activity of the immune system is essential for the success of comprehensive therapy for various pathological conditions [14, 25].

To date, the issues of the etiology and pathogenesis of secondary immunodeficiency syndromes (IDS), despite their relevance and importance, are inadequately covered in the scientific literature. The available data are fragmented, incomplete, and lack specificity [22, 24].

According to research by O. Ch. Chariyev and N. B. Yusupbaev, levamisole affects immunity formation in sheep with babesiosis and piroplasmiasis after the use of adadin and dimedin [2, 4]. G. V. Pavlov and colleagues studied the impact of human recombinant tumor necrosis factor (TNF) on the immune status of cattle with theileriosis. According to the researcher, TNF enhances the antigen-presenting function of macrophages and switches immunoglobulin synthesis from class M to G, enabling a more adequate response and the formation of memory cells [6, 8]. High therapeutic and prophylactic effect was achieved using the immunostimulator Lactolen and the coccidiostatic Stenorol in the treatment of cryptosporidiosis in calves. The immunomodulatory effect of T-activin with Coccicol on the activation of T- and B-lymphocytes in experimental and spontaneous cryptosporidiosis in cattle was established. However, in some cases, the use of immunostimulators does not yield the desired effect, especially when a rapid and significant enhancement of the animals' immune defenses is required [3, 15].

As noted in the reviews by Khaitov P.M. and Pinegin B.V. (1996, 2000), the greatest efficacy of immunotherapy can be expected specifically in secondary or acquired immunodeficiencies. To correct immunodeficient states, a considerable range of drugs has been developed, both synthetic and natural, acting on the main components of the immune system. It is particularly noteworthy that natural (animal and plant) origin agents are especially promising because they exert a mild impact on the bodies of animals and humans, are low-toxic, and provide a stable therapeutic effect [5, 7].

Thus, solving the problems of diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of secondary immune insufficiency depends both on the comprehensive study of morphofunctional indicators of the immune system state under normal and pathological conditions, and on the selection of agents used as immunocorrectors.

Conclusion. Parasitic diseases suppress the immune response, leading to the development of secondary persistent immunodeficiency, which is characterized by a reduction in T-helper cells and a decrease in IgA secretion. During helminth infections, the human body mobilizes all protective mechanisms; however, in some cases, when the struggle with parasites is prolonged, immune responses become inadequate, potentially resulting in immunopathological manifestations and disruptions in the function of various organs.

Based on the presented data, it is advisable to use immunomodulators not only for therapeutic purposes but also as preventive measures in cases of helminth infections, even before the identification of the pathogen at the stage of endogenous invasion. This approach will help maintain a high level of immune competence in the host organism and reduce the negative consequences of infections.

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